

A workflow for quality control in surface texture analysis applied to teeth and tools

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Mountains document for the examples shown in the text.

The three surfaces used here have been acquired in a row: simply clicking 3 times on 'acquire'. See Calandra et al. (2019).

1. Control and clean a height map.

1a. Load first height map (studiable #1): there is no NMP here because all acquired points are kept. Low-quality points will result in outliers (see 3D view), that will be removed in step 1b.

Identity card			
Name:	FLT1-7_location1_LSM_5...replica1_20180815_Topo		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	26.11	μm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.0003985	μm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

1b. Remove outliers.

Operator 'Remove outliers' on studiable #1:
 - maximum slope allowed = 80°
 - strength of the method = soft
 - remove measurement noise

Identity card			
Name:	FLT1-7_location1_LSM_5...Topo > Outliers removed		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	25.74	µm	
Size:	64604	digits	
Spacing:	0.0003985	µm	
NM-points ratio:	6.932 % (623867 Pts)		

2. Extract area from the cleaned height map (step 1b)

Identity card			
Name:	FLT1-7_location1_LS...ved > Extracted area		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	50.00	µm	
Size:	588	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	50.00	µm	
Size:	588	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	9.617	µm	
Size:	24135	digits	
Spacing:	0.0003985	µm	
NM-points ratio:	0.4648 % (1607 Pts)		

3. Combine acquisitions

3a. Same as step 1 with the second height map (studiable #2).
The steps before could be saved as a mini-doc to automatize and apply to other studiables.

Identity card			
Name:	FLT1-7_location1_LSM_5...replica2_20180815_Topo		
File path:	D:\Data\3Ddata\Acquisiti...lica2_20180815_Topo.sur		
Created on:	15/08/2018 16:44:00		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis: X			
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis: Y			
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis: Z			
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	26.41	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.000403	µm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	FLT1-7_location1_LSM_5...Topo > Outliers removed		
File path:	D:\Data\3Ddata\Acquisiti...lica2_20180815_Topo.sur		
Created on:	15/08/2018 16:44:00		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis: X			
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis: Y			
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis: Z			
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	26.07	µm	
Size:	64688	digits	
Spacing:	0.000403	µm	
NM-points ratio:	6.823 % (614058 Pts)		

3b. Same as step 1 with the third height map (studiable #3).

Identity card			
Name:	FLT1-7_location1_LS...lica3_20180815_Topo		
File path:	D:\Data\3Ddata\Acqui..._20180815_Topo.sur		
Created on:	15/08/2018 17:06:24		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	25.88	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.0003949	µm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	FLT1-7_location1_LS...o > Outliers removed		
File path:	D:\Data\3Ddata\Acqui..._20180815_Topo.sur		
Created on:	15/08/2018 17:06:24		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	25.62	µm	
Size:	64894	digits	
Spacing:	0.0003949	µm	
NM-points ratio:	6.885 % (619623 Pts)		

3c. The 3 outlier-free studiabler (steps 1b, 3a & 3b) must now be combined into a series of surfaces.

The operator 'build series' is part of the '4D series' module.

3d. Align the 3 outlier-free studiabler. Without this step, the combination of the surfaces later might combine pixels from different positions!

The operator 'Shift surfaces' is used for this purpose:

- studiabler #1 is the reference
- rotation and offset settings computed automatically (fine for small rotation and offset)
- the intersection is kept (i.e. the area present on all surfaces)

3e. Combine the shifted surfaces by extracting the 'mean surface of the series'. The operator 'Extract surface' is used for this.

For every point, the mean height of the 3 surfaces will be calculated. If there is no value for 1 or 2 surfaces, the height of the point(s) of the remaining surface(s) will be used. In other words, the resulting surface will contain NMP only for the points where all 3 surfaces had NMP.

Identity card			
Name:	FLT1-7_location1_LS...series > Mean surface		
Studiabale type:	Surface		
Axis: X			
Length:	254.5	µm	
Size:	2988	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis: Y			
Length:	254.5	µm	
Size:	2988	points	
Spacing:	0.08519	µm	
Axis: Z			
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	25.77	µm	
Size:	63941	digits	
Spacing:	0.000403	µm	
NM-points ratio:	0.9404 % (83956 Pts)		

Notice that the XY size of the resulting surface is slightly smaller than the original size. This is because we kept the intersection during shifting (see above).

3f. Graphical summary of the workflow using the studies 'History of current studiable'.

